

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

U.G'.Otabekov

FORMATION OF STUDENTS' KNOWLEDGE AND SKILLS IN ENGINEERING
SCIENCES AND COMPUTER GRAPHICS DISCIPLINES BASED ON A
PSYCHOLOGICAL APPROACH

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

Bosh muharrir:
A.A. Abdurahmonov

2023/APREL

HONORED
MENTION

YOUR
SEAL